

MultiXscale

Portable test suite for shared software stack

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Executive Summary

The European Environment for Scientific Software Installations (EESSI) test suite consists of three main parts: EESSI test suite logic, the test classes themselves, and some auxiliary files (configuration, scripts easily enabling periodic runs of the test suite, etc).

One of the main focus points in developing the EESSI test suite was to ensure portability of tests. ReFrame tests traditionally contain a large amount of system-specific information. The paradigm followed by the EESSI test suite is that all system specific information is limited to the ReFrame configuration files that describe the system, so that the test classes themselves only contain generalizable information. As an example: instead of specifying a hardcoded number of tasks to run a test with (the traditional ReFrame approach), tests in the EESSI mixin class may declare that they 'run on a full node, with one task per core'. The EESSI Mixin class then reads the configuration for the system it is running on, and translates this to a concrete task count.

While the implementation of the EESSI Mixin class was one of the key changes since the publication of D1.2, several other features were added as well that facilitate test development (e.g. memory usage reporting), improve test performance (e.g. process binding, improved support for hyperthreading systems) or improve usability (lower chance of out-of-memory errors since tests declare their memory requirement, improved logging, being able to run the test suite on a local module stack, more efficient staging).

A total of 10 applications are now supported in the test suite. To get better coverage, community contributions are essential. Thus, substantial attention has been paid to aspects that may increase community uptake. This includes trying to make test development simpler, simplify running the test suite on a local software stack, and outreach in the form of a hands-on session.

In summary, the EESSI test suite provides a portable test suite with key applications that are important to MultiXscale. It has solved the portability challenge through the implementation of the EESSI Mixin class, and portability was proven by running across a wide range of systems.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable describes the development of the EESSI test suite: a portable test suite created to test the software in the shared software stack. It also discusses how the test suite is employed in practice, and our efforts to attract community contributions. The work presented here was executed in the context of Task 1.3 - "Design and creation of a software test suite and facilitating Continuous Integration (CI) for software developers".

1.2 Target audience of the deliverable

This deliverable is targeted at readers with experience in High Performance Computing (HPC) system support, particularly in the context of maintaining and testing software stacks (or specific applications) for HPC infrastructure.

1.3 Deliverable outline

Section 2 describes the (code) structure of the EESSI test suite. Section 3 describes how we achieve portability, and discuss two important components that provide portability (the ReFrame configuration file, and the EESSI Mixin class). Section 4 discusses other key features of the EESSI test suite. In section 5 we list the applications that are currently supported in the EESSI test suite. Section 6 discusses what has been done to stimulate uptake of the EESSI test suite by the community in order to foster sustainability.

1.4 Partner contributions

SURF and UGent contributed as planned to the work in this deliverable. Note that Task 1.3 had other partners (RIJK-SUNIGRON, Bsc), but those were never envisioned to contribute to the EESSI test suite itself - they developed other components within Task 1.3.

2 Structure of the test suite

In this section, we discuss the structure of the test suite. Understanding the structure of the test suite is helpful in understanding how the test suite works.

The key directory and file structure of the test suite repository [1] is as follows:

```

1 CI/<site>_<system_name>/ci_config.sh
2 CI/run_reframe.sh
3 CI/run_reframe_wrapper.sh
4 config/<site>_<system_name>.py
5 eessi/testsuite/tests/
6 eessi/testsuite/common_config.py
7 eessi/testsuite/constants.py
8 eessi/testsuite/eessi_mixin.py
9 eessi/testsuite/hooks.py
10 eessi/testsuite/utils.py

```

2.1 ReFrame test classes

The core part of the test suite are the test definitions and resources under `eessi/testsuite/tests/`. Each test is essentially a class definition that inherits from a ReFrame test class. Some tests come with resources, e.g. input files, which are also stored in this subdirectory. Typically, tests for a single application are defined in a single python file, but multiple test classes may be defined for a single application. For example, the file `eessi/testsuite/tests/apps/osu.py` includes tests for the OSU Microbenchmarks both for point-to-point and collective communication, each of which is defined in a separate test class.

2.2 EESSI test suite logic

The EESSI test suite is not a standard ReFrame test suite: it implements additional logic and configuration in order to achieve portability. This is achieved through `eessi/testsuite/common_config.py`, `eessi/testsuite/constants.py`, `eessi/testsuite/eessi_mixin.py`, `eessi/testsuite/hooks.py` and `eessi/testsuite/utils.py`.

2.3 Reframe configuration files

The `config` directory contains a number of configuration files for systems on which the EESSI test suite has been deployed in the context of the MultiXscale project. These serve both as examples for other users, and at the same time allows us to have version-controlled configuration files.

2.4 Facilitating periodic runs

Everything under the `CI` directory is intended to make it easy to set up periodic (e.g. daily or weekly) runs on a system. The `CI/<site>_<system_name>/ci_config.sh` script allows one to set a configuration for these periodic runs. For example, these configuration items can be used to determine which version of the test suite to run, which version of ReFrame to use, which arguments to pass to ReFrame (e.g. for running a subset of the tests), etc. The `CI/run_reframe.sh` and `run_reframe_wrapper.sh` scripts are the main drivers of these periodic runs. Based on the configuration, they create installations of ReFrame, the test suite, and running everything with the desired arguments. It also sets defaults for all configuration items not explicitly defined in `ci_config.sh`.

With this, setting up a periodic run as e.g. a cronjob can be as simple as:

1. Cloning the `CI` subdirectory of the repository;
2. Creating a `ci_config.sh` config file for the system (if none is present yet in the test-suite repository);
3. Adding a line like


```
0 0 * * * EESSI_CI_SYSTEM_NAME=surf_snellius $HOME/test-suite/CI/run_reframe_wrapper.sh
```

 to your crontab file.

3 Portability

3.1 Overcoming the portability challenge

In order to create a *portable* test suite, it is of paramount importance that system-specific information and test-specific information is clearly separated. In the EESSI test suite, that is achieved by making sure that all system-specific information is provided through the ReFrame configuration file, while all the test-specific information is contained within the (ReFrame) test classes.

This means that tests should be developed in such a way that they can take the information provided in the ReFrame configuration file, and *do something sensible* based on that. For example, if a test requires 200 GB of memory to run, but the ReFrame configuration file states that a given partition only provides 100 GB, the test should be skipped. Another example would be a program that uses pure MPI parallelism, where one typically wants to launch one task per available physical core. The test should then read the number of available cores from the ReFrame configuration file, and determine the number of tasks to be launched for the test accordingly.

Note that this approach to achieving portability is sufficient because this is a *test suite*, not a *benchmark suite*. A test suite is meant to allow identification of (performance) *regressions*, whereas a benchmark is meant to show the absolute-best performance one can achieve for a given application on a given system. The latter typically requires manual tuning. For example, a task binding strategy that is optimal on system A is not necessarily optimal on system B. For the test suite, we just set a binding strategy that is expected to give reasonable performance on any system - but more importantly that is expected to result in *reproducible* performance: the more stable the performance, the smaller the performance regressions that one can identify.

3.2 Configuring the EESSI test suite

While the EESSI test suite uses standard ReFrame configuration files, it does impose additional constraints. ReFrame allows certain fields to be defined as key-value pairs, i.e. free text. The EESSI test suite standardizes these key value pairs through constants defined in `eessi/testsuite/constants.py`. This allows us to assign meaning to those free text labels.

Typically, the following sections that are specific to the EESSI test suite should be set in the ReFrame configuration file:

```

1 'systems': [
2 ...
3     'partitions': [
4         {
5             'prepare_cmds': [common_eessi_init()],
6             'resources': [
7                 {
8                     'name': 'memory',
9                     'options': ['--mem={size}']
10                }
11            ]
12            'features': [
13                FEATURES.CPU,
14                ] + list(SCALES.keys()),
15            'extras': {
16                EXTRAS.MEM_PER_NODE: 229376 # in MiB
17            },
18            ...
19        ]
20    ],
21 ],
22 'logging': common_logging_config(reframe_prefix),
23 'general': [
24     {
25         'remote_detect': True,
26         **common_general_config(reframe_prefix)
27     }
28 ],

```

- The `common_eessi_init()` is a common set of initialization commands that checks what EESSI environment is initialized on the node running the `reframe` command (typically a login node), and makes sure the same EESSI environment is initialized on the batch nodes.
- The memory resource defines the flag that should be passed to the given resource schedule to ask for a certain amount of memory per node. This can then be used by test classes to *try* and request sufficient memory to run a test.

- The `features` list includes e.g. if a partition should run CPU tests (`FEATURES.CPU`), GPU tests (`FEATURES.GPU`) or both, and at what scales. A set of default test scales is defined that ranges from a single core to 16 full nodes, but on small systems one can pass a subset of this list to limit the maximum size of tests being run.
- The `EXTRAS.MEM_PER_NODE` item defines the *maximum* amount of memory per node that a job can ask for on that partition. The test suite uses this information to skip tests that require more memory than that.
- The `remote_detect: True` item tells ReFrame to automatically detect the CPU topology on the partition. ReFrame stores this information in a separate file, which then describes things like the number of cores per node, number of cores per socket, number of numa domains, etc.

All of the `common_*` functions are defined in `eessi/testsuite/common_config.py` and make sure that the general behavior of the system on different systems is similar, thus providing predictability in e.g. what items are logged, where, etc.

With these few key items in the ReFrame configuration file, we can achieve test portability: we can ensure that tests only run if the required resources (GPUs, sufficient memory) are present, and we can ensure that a sensible number of tasks / thread for that system are launched (by using the detected CPU topology).

Note that additional `features` and `extras` may be added in future test suite releases, as needed. E.g. for now, the shared software stack only has support for NVIDIA GPUs, and thus a general `FEATURES.GPU` is sufficiently specific. In the future, more specific features may be defined to provide more fine-grained control, e.g. `'FEATURES.NVIDIA_GPU'`, `'FEATURES.AMD_GPU'`, etc.

3.3 EESSI Mixin class

In Deliverable D 1.2, a proof of concept for a portable test for GRONingen MACHine for Chemical Simulation (GROMACS) was presented. Since then, tests for several other applications were added (Section 5). As more tests were added, it became clear there was a fair amount of duplication of logic between these tests. Thus, the code was refactored and the common logic between these tests classes that is needed to make the tests portable was separated into a so-called Mixin class. The result is that the test classes became more lightweight, and focussed on configuration rather than logic. E.g. a test can declare through a simple variable assignment that it requires a GPU. The logic in the EESSI Mixin class then makes sure this test is filtered out on partitions that do not offer any GPUs. For example, the implementation of the GROMACS test class in Appendix A is now inheriting from the EESSI mixin class, and is substantially more compact that it was before (see Deliverable 1.2, Appendix A).

An additional advantage of the EESSI Mixin class is that it makes writing the portable tests easier, for two reasons:

1. Writing a test class is now (mostly) done by just defining the required class properties (i.e. configuration).
2. The EESSI Mixin class has internal checks to make sure the inheriting class defines the correct properties at the correct stage of the ReFrame pipeline, and that the values assigned to those properties are valid. It gives verbose feedback if a certain keyword hasn't been assigned in a timely fashion or has an invalid value. Thus, even without reading the documentation, a test developer is guided through the development process.

For example, the EESSI Mixin class defines the following ReFrame pipeline hook that is run after the 'init' stage of the ReFrame pipeline:

```

1  @run_after('init')
2  def EESSI_mixin_validate_init(self):
3      """Check that all variables that have to be set for subsequent hooks in the init phase have been set"""
4      # List which variables we will need/use in the run_after('init') hooks
5      var_list = ['device_type', 'scale', 'module_name', 'measure_memory_usage']
6      for var in var_list:
7          if not hasattr(self, var):
8              msg = "The variable '%s' should be defined in any test class that inherits" % var
9              msg += " from EESSI_Mixin before (or in) the init phase, but it wasn't"
10             raise ReframeFatalError(msg)
11
12     # Check that the value for these variables is valid,
13     # i.e. exists in their respective dict from eessi.testsuite.constants
14     self.EESSI_mixin_validate_item_in_list('device_type', DEVICE_TYPES[:])
15     self.EESSI_mixin_validate_item_in_list('scale', SCALES.keys())
16     self.EESSI_mixin_validate_item_in_list('valid_systems', [['*'])
17     self.EESSI_mixin_validate_item_in_list('valid_prog_environs', [['default']])

```

Essentially, this hook checks that for any test inheriting from EESSI mixin, the class attributes `device_type`, `scale`, `valid_systems` and `valid_prog_environs` have been defined, and their value is valid. If a test developer fails to assign one of these keywords, or assigns an invalid value, the EESSI Mixin class will raise a clear error.

Subsequently, the EESSI Mixin class calls the following ReFrame pipeline hook:

```
1 @run_after('init')
2 def EESSI_mixin_run_after_init(self):
3     """Hooks to run after init phase"""
4
5     # Filter on which scales are supported by the partitions defined in the ReFrame configuration
6     hooks.filter_supported_scales(self)
7
8     hooks.filter_valid_systems_by_device_type(self, required_device_type=self.device_type)
9
10    hooks.set_modules(self)
11
12    # Set scales as tags
13    hooks.set_tag_scale(self)
```

Each of the functions from the `hooks` namespace can now safely assume that the four aforementioned class attributes are set.

To show how this simplifies the test development, consider the [mpi4py tutorial test that is in the EESSI documentation](#) (the final test from this tutorial is included in Appendix B). The only thing this class now needs to define for the init pipeline hook is:

```
1 device_type = DEVICE_TYPES.CPU
```

It does not need to call any of the `hooks` functions itself, nor does it need to define the other three properties (`scale`, `valid_systems` and `valid_prog_environs`): the `EESSI Mixin` class provides defaults - overwriting these is optional.

Overall, the tutorial test is a clear example of how the `EESSI Mixin` class simplifies the test: the original test (before inheriting from the `EESSI Mixin` class) was 43 lines of code initially, and is reduced to only 21 lines of code (see Appendix B) after using the `EESSI Mixin` class.

4 Other notable features

While the implementation and adoption of the EESSI Mixin class was the most prominent feature that was implemented since the publication of Deliverable D1.2, various other smaller features were added as well.

4.1 Declaring test memory requirement

ReFrame tests always request a certain number of tasks and CPUs per task. Typically, schedulers allocate a default amount of memory per CPU core in the allocation. This amount is however not always sufficient to run a particular test. For example, a test may request only 5% of the available cores on a node, but require 10% of the node memory. Such a test would fail with an out-of-memory error if one relies on the default amount of allocated memory.

To resolve this, tests now declare the amount of memory required per node (optionally as a function of the number of tasks). It is the responsibility of the test contributor to define the memory requirement in the test class. For example, the GROMACS test declares that it requires 1024 MiB per task:

```
1 def required_mem_per_node(self):  
2     return self.num_tasks_per_node * 1024
```

The EESSI Mixin class uses this information in two ways. First, it checks against the ReFrame configuration if the maximum amount of memory that is allocatable per node is sufficient. If not, the test is skipped. If there is sufficient allocatable memory, it will compute the default memory available per CPU and compare this to the required amount of memory by the test. It will then request the maximum of these two numbers from the batch scheduler.

4.2 Memory usage reporting

It may be tricky for test developers to figure out the memory scaling (as function of the number of tasks) for their tests. To facilitate this, the EESSI Mixin class has functionality to report maximum memory used by the test. Users can simply set the maximum amount of memory available per node in an initial run, and then pass `--setvar measure_memory_usage=True` as an extra argument in their ReFrame run. This way, each of the tests will report the maximum amount of memory that was *actually* used. That information can then be used to specify the *actual* memory requirement in the test class.

Note that this functionality requires that the test is run in a Linux Control Group (cgroup). Since most modern HPC systems use cgroups for managing job allocations, this requirement is easily met. Note also that none of the current tests set this by default: this feature mainly exists to be used during test *development*, to come up with a reasonable test memory requirement declaration, and is thus typically only enabled through overriding the variable with the ‘`--setvar`’ approach mentioned before.

4.3 Process binding

Although the optimal process binding strategy may differ per system, declaring at least a *fixed* process binding strategy in a test will improve reproducibility of the test results. By default, the EESSI Mixin class now ensures compact process binding if a supported parallel launcher is used (currently: `srun`, Intel’s `mpirun` or OpenMPI’s `mpirun`).

Currently, the EESSI Mixin class sets compact process binding by default for *all* tests. Other binding options may later be implemented in the EESSI Mixin class, in which case the binding strategy will become another mandatory parameter for tests inheriting from the EESSI Mixin class.

4.4 Improved logging

A change in test performance can be caused by a change in the software being used (e.g. version, micro-architecture optimization, etc), the underlying system (e.g. OS update, etc), or the test suite itself (e.g. change in binding behavior between versions). To be able to better identify what caused a change in performance, the EESSI Mixin class now logs the following information for each test:

- CernVM File System (CernVM-FS) repository name (if any);
- Software subdirectory of the EESSI repository that is providing the software (the micro-architecture optimization can be inferred from this);
- Full path to the module file;
- Version of the EESSI test suite being used;

The first two of these are specific to running the test suite on the EESSI software stack, the others are also relevant when running the test suite on a local module stack (see next section).

4.5 Flexible initialization

Previously, the default initialization of the environment on a batch node would load the EESSI software environment, and was thus only suitable for running the test suite on the EESSI software stack. The EESSI test suite now better supports running on a local module stack, rather than the EESSI software stack. This increases the impact of the EESSI test suite, as HPC support teams may now use the test suite to test their local software stack, even if they don't use EESSI.

4.6 More efficiently handling of staged files

By default, ReFrame stages files for every instance of a test. E.g. if a test is run at 10 different scales, the same files will be staged 10 times, in 10 different subdirectories. This is necessary if, and only if, the tests write to those files. However, in practice, many tests only read from a set of input files. The ReFrame test attribute `readonly_files` may be used for this purpose: anything that's listed in `readonly_files` will not be staged, but read directly from the source directory, thus saving excessive copying. The EESSI Mixin class now enforces that any test set this attribute explicitly,

```
1 def __init_subclass__(cls, **kwargs):
2     ...
3     if not cls.readonly_files:
4         msg = ''.join([
5             "Built-in attribute 'readonly_files' is empty. To avoid excessive copying, it's highly recommended
6             ",
7             "to add all files and/or dirs in 'sourcedir' that are needed but not modified during the test,",
8             "thus can be symlinked into the stage dirs. If you are sure there are no such files,",
9             "set 'readonly_files = []'."
10        ])
11        raise ReframeFatalError(msg)
```

thus enforcing test developers to actively consider if all files need to be staged or not.

4.7 Improved support for hyperthreading systems

It is quite common for pure MPI tests to launch 1 task per CPU core. On hyperthreading systems, ReFrame recognizes every hardware thread as a "CPU". However, the most sensible default is typically to launch 1 task per *physical* CPU core on such systems, since this leads to the best reproducibility in test performance. Test developers can now *choose* if their test should launch one task per physical CPU, or per hardware thread. All tests currently in the test suite do this, as none of the tests show a performance benefit when launching one task per hardware thread.

5 Supported applications

The latest release of the portable test suite contains tests for the following applications [2]:

- CP2K
- ESPResSo
- GROMACS
- LAMMPS
- MetalWalls
- OpenFOAM
- OSU Microbenchmarks
- PyTorch
- QuantumESPRESSO
- TensorFlow

Note that since these are high-level applications (except for one which is a benchmarking tool), these tests indirectly test a wide range of lower level dependencies as well.

While the test suite is open source, and welcomes contributions for any application available in EESSI, the effort in Task 1.3 focused on tests that are relevant for MultiXscale. This includes applications developed or used in MultiXscale, but also applications that are so well known or widely used (e.g. TensorFlow, PyTorch, GROMACS) that their inclusion can increase the potential uptake of EESSI and the EESSI test suite.

6 Community building and sustainability

Since the EESSI test suite is portable, it is potentially useful to HPC support teams that maintain a software stack and that would like to test that stack. This means that the test suite provides a unique opportunity for HPC support teams to share effort in *software testing*, much in the same way that EasyBuild and EESSI allow sharing effort in *building software*.

Building a community around the EESSI test suite has two advantages for the test suite itself:

- The test suite can support more applications, since contributing the tests is a shared effort and different contributors may have experience with different software;
- The more people use the test suite, the more sustainable it becomes.

While it is impossible to *guarantee* uptake by the HPC community, we make an effort to encourage this as much as we can, through numerous decisions and features:

- The EESSI Mixin class simplifies test development, since it is largely limited to setting attributes in the test class. Very little programming / logic is needed, as this is taken care of by the EESSI Mixin class.
- One step in running the test suite is discovery of the installed modules, so that tests are only generated for applications that are available in the environment. There are only two assumptions made here: that the software is installed with EasyBuild, and that a flat module naming scheme is used (a condition that could possibly be relaxed in the future). Because many systems satisfy this assumption, there is a large potential group of users for the EESSI test suite.
- There is extensive documentation both on how to run the test suite, and how to contribute new tests (including a tutorial test) [3].
- The EESSI Mixin class is very verbose in indicating missing attributes in an inheriting test. This means contributors do not have to read the full documentation, but can look up the meaning of specific attributes as needed.
- We have organized a short hands-on session at the 10th EasyBuild User Meeting [4], in which attendees had a chance to try and run the EESSI test suite on their own HPC system and software stack. Since this is a community that has a focus on building software, they generally also have an interest in testing their installations.

7 Conclusion and outlook

The EESSI test suite is a portable test suite that currently supports 10 software applications. The portability is clear from the fact that it is deployed on 13 systems, ranging from European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC) systems, to HPC systems of project partners and a cluster in the cloud setup. The current deployments of the test suite provide quality assurance for the EESSI software, both as part of the software deployment procedure, as well as continuously through periodic testing.

While community building is notoriously difficult, a lot of attention has been given to making sure the test suite is easy to use, adopt, and expand. Also, we have and will continue to spread awareness about the EESSI test suite in the HPC community.

A The EESSI test suite GROMACS test

Here, we provide the Python code for the EESSI GROMACS test, after being refactored to use the EESSI Mixin class. This code is included here to illustrate the relative simplicity of a test using the EESSI Mixin class. For comparison with how this portable test looked *before* the EESSI Mixin class was introduced, see Appendix A of Deliverable 1.2. Note that, since the prior version in Deliverable 1.2, the class body is now only 42 lines of code (compared to 69 lines of code before), despite the fact that additional features were added (e.g. to handle skipping the test when insufficient memory is available).

```

1 import reframe as rfm
2 from reframe.core.builtins import parameter, run_after # added only to make the linter happy
3
4 from hpctestlib.sciapps.gromacs.benchmarks import gromacs_check
5
6 from eessi.testsuite.constants import COMPUTE_UNITS, DEVICE_TYPES, SCALES
7 from eessi.testsuite.eessi_mixin import EESSI_Mixin
8 from eessi.testsuite.utils import find_modules, log
9
10
11 class EESSI_GROMACS_base(gromacs_check):
12     @run_after('init')
13     def set_device_type(self):
14         self.device_type = self.nb_impl
15
16
17 @rfm.simple_test
18 class EESSI_GROMACS(EESSI_GROMACS_base, EESSI_Mixin):
19     scale = parameter(SCALES.keys())
20     time_limit = '30m'
21     module_name = parameter(find_modules('GROMACS'))
22     bench_name_ci = 'HECBioSim/Crambin'
23     # input files are downloaded
24     readonly_files = ['']
25     # executable_opts in addition to those set by the hpctestlib
26     executable_opts = ['-dlb', 'yes', '-npme', '-1']
27
28     def required_mem_per_node(self):
29         return self.num_tasks_per_node * 1024
30
31     def __init__(self):
32         # self.device_type must be set before the @run_after('init') hooks of the EESSI_Mixin class
33         self.device_type = self.nb_impl
34
35     @run_after('init')
36     def set_compute_unit(self):
37         """
38         Set the compute unit to which tasks will be assigned:
39         one task per CPU core for CPU runs, and one task per GPU for GPU runs.
40         """
41         if self.device_type == DEVICE_TYPES.CPU:
42             self.compute_unit = COMPUTE_UNITS.CPU
43         elif self.device_type == DEVICE_TYPES.GPU:
44             self.compute_unit = COMPUTE_UNITS.GPU
45         else:
46             msg = f"No mapping of device type {self.device_type} to a COMPUTE_UNITS was specified in this test"
47             raise NotImplementedError(msg)
48
49     @run_after('setup')
50     def set_omp_num_threads(self):
51         """
52         Set number of OpenMP threads.
53         Set both OMP_NUM_THREADS and -ntomp explicitly to avoid conflicting values.
54         Set default number of OpenMP threads equal to number of CPUs per task.
55         Also support setting OpenMP threads on the cmd line via custom executable option '-ntomp'.
56         """
57         omp_num_threads = self.num_cpus_per_task
58         self.executable_opts += ['-ntomp', str(omp_num_threads)]
59         log(f'executable_opts set to {self.executable_opts}')
60
61         self.env_vars['OMP_NUM_THREADS'] = omp_num_threads
62         log(f'env_vars set to {self.env_vars}')

```

B The tutorial test: mpi4py

Here, we provide the Python code for the EESSI mpi4py test, which serves as a tutorial in the documentation. Below, we show two versions: first, the version without using the EESSI Mixin class, then, the version that inherits from the EESSI Mixin class. This code is included here to illustrate the relative simplicity of a test using the EESSI Mixin class.

```

1 import reframe as rfm
2 import reframe.utility.sanity as sn
3
4 # added only to make the linter happy
5 from reframe.core.builtins import variable, parameter, run_after, performance_function, sanity_function
6
7 from eessi.testsuite import hooks
8 from eessi.testsuite.constants import SCALES, COMPUTE_UNITS
9 from eessi.testsuite.utils import find_modules
10
11
12 # This python decorator indicates to ReFrame that this class defines a test
13 # Our class inherits from rfm.RunOnlyRegressionTest, since this test does not have a compilation stage
14 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.
    RunOnlyRegressionTest
15 @rfm.simple_test
16 class EESSI_MPI4PY(rfm.RunOnlyRegressionTest):
17     # Programming environments are only relevant for tests that compile something
18     # Since we are testing existing modules, we typically don't compile anything and simply define
19     # 'default' as the valid programming environment
20     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    valid_prog_environs
21     valid_prog_environs = ['default']
22
23     # Typically, we list here the name of our cluster as it is specified in our ReFrame configuration file
24     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    valid_systems
25     valid_systems = ['*']
26
27     # ReFrame will generate a test for each module
28     # NOTE: each parameter adds a new dimension to the parametrization space.
29     # (EG 4 parameters with (3,3,2,2) possible values will result in 36 tests).
30     # Be mindful of how many parameters you add to avoid the number of tests generated being excessive.
31     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.parameter
    module_name = parameter(find_modules('mpi4py'))
32
33
34     # ReFrame will generate a test for each scale
35     scale = parameter(SCALES.keys())
36
37     # Our script has two arguments, --n_iter and --n_warmup. By defining these as ReFrame variables, we can
38     # enable the end-user to overwrite their value on the command line when invoking ReFrame.
39     # Note that we don't typically expose ALL variables, especially if a script has many - we expose
40     # only those that we think an end-user might want to overwrite
41     # Number of iterations to run (more iterations takes longer, but results in more accurate timing)
42     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.variable
    n_iterations = variable(int, value=1000)
43
44
45     # Similar for the number of warmup iterations
46     n_warmup = variable(int, value=100)
47
48     # Define which executable to run
49     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    executable
50     executable = 'python3'
51
52     # Define which options to pass to the executable
53     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    executable_opts
54     executable_opts = ['mpi4py_reduce.py', '--n_iter', f'{n_iterations}', '--n_warmup', f'{n_warmup}']
55
56     # Temporarily define postrun_cmds to make it easy to find out memory usage
57     postrun_cmds = [
58         # for cgroups v1
59         'MAX_MEM_IN_BYTES=$(</sys/fs/cgroup/memory/$(</proc/self/cpuset)/../memory.max_usage_in_bytes)',
60         # for cgroups v2
61         '# 'MAX_MEM_IN_BYTES=$(</sys/fs/cgroup/$(</proc/self/cpuset)/../../../../memory.peak)',
62         'echo "MAX_MEM_IN_BYTES=$MAX_MEM_IN_BYTES"',
63         'echo "MAX_MEM_IN_MIB=$((MAX_MEM_IN_BYTES/1048576))"'
64     ]

```

```

65
66 # Define a time limit for the scheduler running this test
67 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
68 time_limit
69 time_limit = '5m00s'
70
71 @run_after('init')
72 def set_modules(self):
73     hooks.set_modules(self)
74
75 # Using this decorator, we tell ReFrame to run this AFTER the init step of the test
76 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.run_after
77 # See https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/pipeline.html for all steps in the pipeline
78 # that reframe uses to execute tests.
79 @run_after('init')
80 def run_after_init(self):
81     hooks.set_tag_scale(self)
82
83 @run_after('setup')
84 def set_num_tasks_per_node(self):
85     """ Setting number of tasks per node and cpus per task in this function. This function sets
86     num_tasks, num_tasks_per_node, num_cpus_per_task, and num_gpus_per_node, based on the current scale
87     and the current partition's num_cpus, max_avail_gpus_per_node and num_nodes"""
88     hooks.assign_tasks_per_compute_unit(self, COMPUTE_UNITS.CPU)
89
90     # This test scales almost indefinitely
91     # For tests that have limited scaling, make sure that test instances exceeding
92     # a predefined maximum task count are skipped using:
93     # max_tasks = 300
94     # self.skip_if(self.num_tasks > max_tasks,
95     #               f'Skipping test: more than {max_tasks} tasks are requested ({self.num_tasks})')
96
97 # Make sure we request sufficient memory from the scheduler
98 @run_after('setup')
99 def request_mem(self):
100     mem_required = self.num_tasks_per_node * 256 # request 256 MB per task per node
101     hooks.req_memory_per_node(self, app_mem_req=mem_required)
102
103 # Set binding strategy
104 @run_after('setup')
105 def set_binding(self):
106     hooks.set_compact_process_binding(self)
107
108 # Now, we check if the pattern 'Sum of all ranks: X' with X the correct sum for the amount of ranks is found
109 # in the standard output:
110 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.sanity_function
111 @sanity_function
112 def validate(self):
113     # Sum of 0, ..., N-1 is (N * (N-1) / 2)
114     sum_of_ranks = round(self.num_tasks * ((self.num_tasks - 1) / 2))
115     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/deferrable_functions_reference.html#reframe.utility.sanity.
116     assert_found
117     return sn.assert_found(r'Sum of all ranks: %s' % sum_of_ranks, self.stdout)
118
119 # Now, we define a pattern to extract a number that reflects the performance of this test
120 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.
121 performance_function
122 @performance_function('s')
123 def time(self):
124     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/deferrable_functions_reference.html#reframe.utility.sanity.
125     extractsingle
126     return sn.extractsingle(r'^Time elapsed:\s+(?P<perf>\S+)', self.stdout, 'perf', float)
127
128 @performance_function('MiB')
129 def max_mem_in_mib(self):
130     return sn.extractsingle(r'^MAX_MEM_IN_MIB=(?P<perf>\S+)', self.stdout, 'perf', int)
131
132 import reframe as rfm
133 import reframe.utility.sanity as sn
134
135 # added only to make the linter happy
136 from reframe.core.builtins import variable, parameter, performance_function, sanity_function
137
138 # Import the EESSI_Mixin class so that we can inherit from it
139 from eessi.testsuite.eessi_mixin import EESSI_Mixin
140 from eessi.testsuite.constants import COMPUTE_UNITS, DEVICE_TYPES
141 from eessi.testsuite.utils import find_modules

```

```

11
12
13 # This python decorator indicates to ReFrame that this class defines a test
14 # Our class inherits from rfm.RunOnlyRegressionTest, since this test does not have a compilation stage
15 # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.
    RunOnlyRegressionTest
16 @rfm.simple_test
17 class EESSI_MPI4PY(rfm.RunOnlyRegressionTest, EESSI_Mixin):
18
19     # The device type makes sure this test only gets executed on systems/partitions that can provide this device
20     device_type = DEVICE_TYPES.CPU
21
22     # One task is launched per compute unit. In this case, one task per (physical) CPU core
23     compute_unit = COMPUTE_UNITS.CPU
24
25     # ReFrame will generate a test for each module that matches the regex 'mpi4py'
26     # This means we implicitly assume that any module matching this name provides the required functionality
27     # to run this test
28     module_name = parameter(find_modules('mpi4py'))
29
30     # Our script has two arguments, --n_iter and --n_warmup. By defining these as ReFrame variables, we can
31     # enable the end-user to overwrite their value on the command line when invoking ReFrame.
32     # Note that we don't typically expose ALL variables, especially if a script has many - we expose
33     # only those that we think an end-user might want to overwrite
34     # Number of iterations to run (more iterations takes longer, but results in more accurate timing)
35     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.variable
36     n_iterations = variable(int, value=1000)
37
38     # Similar for the number of warmup iterations
39     n_warmup = variable(int, value=100)
40
41     # Define which executable to run
42     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    executable
43     executable = 'python3'
44
45     # Define which options to pass to the executable
46     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    executable_opts
47     executable_opts = ['mpi4py_reduce.py', '--n_iter', f'{n_iterations}', '--n_warmup', f'{n_warmup}']
48
49     # Define a time limit for the scheduler running this test
50     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.pipeline.RegressionTest.
    time_limit
51     time_limit = '5m00s'
52
53     # Define the benchmarks that are available in the test.
54     # In this test ('EESSI_MPI4PY') there is only one benchmark. If there are more than one,
55     # define them using the 'parameter()' function.
56     bench_name = 'mpi4pi'
57
58     # Specify the benchmark to be tested in CI (will be marked with a 'CI' tag).
59     bench_name_ci = 'mpi4pi'
60
61     # Define the files and/or dirs inside sourcedir (default=src) that should be symlinked into the stage dir
62     readonly_files = ['mpi4py_reduce.py']
63
64     # Define the class method that returns the required memory per node
65     def required_mem_per_node(self):
66         return self.num_tasks_per_node * 100 + 250
67
68     # Now, we check if the pattern 'Sum of all ranks: X' with X the correct sum for the amount of ranks is found
69     # in the standard output:
70     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.sanity_function
    @sanity_function
71     def validate(self):
72         # Sum of 0, ..., N-1 is (N * (N-1) / 2)
73         sum_of_ranks = round(self.num_tasks * ((self.num_tasks - 1) / 2))
74         # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/deferrable_functions_reference.html#reframe.utility.sanity.
    assert_found
75         assert_found
76         return sn.assert_found(r'Sum of all ranks: %s' % sum_of_ranks, self.stdout)
77
78     # Now, we define a pattern to extract a number that reflects the performance of this test
79     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/regression_test_api.html#reframe.core.builtins.
    performance_function
80     @performance_function('s')

```

```
81 def time(self):
82     # https://reframe-hpc.readthedocs.io/en/stable/deferrable\_functions\_reference.html#reframe.utility.sanity.extractsingle
83     return sn.extractsingle(r'^Time elapsed:\s+(?P<perf>\S+)', self.stdout, 'perf', float)
```

References

Acronyms used

CI Continuous Integration

CernVM-FS CernVM File System

EESSI European Environment for Scientific Software Installations

HPC High Performance Computing

EuroHPC European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking

Software mentioned

GROMACS GRoningen MACHine for Chemical Simulation

URLs referenced

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<https://www.multixscale.eu> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu>

<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>

Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/multixscale/planning/issues/105>

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mpi4py tutorial test that is in the EESSI documentation ... <https://www.eessi.io/docs/test-suite/writing-portable-step-by-step-tutorial-for-writing-a-portable-reframe-test>

Citations

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